

ELIXIR Report of the 22nd RDA Plenary

ELIXIR RDA Focus Group

RDA Plenary 22 report

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Introduction

This document has been prepared by [ELIXIR's RDA Activities Focus Group](#) to showcase the synergies and activities of the [Research Data Alliance \(RDA\)](#) which may be useful for ELIXIR members operating in the life sciences domain. The RDA was launched as a community-driven initiative in 2013 with the goal of building the social and technical infrastructure to enable open sharing and re-use of data. The ELIXIR RDA Activities Focus Group has prepared 21 reports of [RDA Plenary events](#) to date containing overviews of highlighted RDA recommendations and outputs. This report contains highlights from various sessions of the RDA 21st Plenary which took place virtually between 14-23 May, 2024. Additional links to collaborative note documents and/or abstracts provided by the session chairs are included within.

About the 22nd RDA Plenary

The 22nd RDA Plenary was a fully virtual event with online only participation for engaging in sessions and accessing recordings using the [Whova](#) conferencing platform. General event highlights have been provided by the RDA and are [available online](#).

The organisers reported impressive engagement in this year's event:

- 500 global participants
- Attendance from 47 countries
- 6 Plenary meetings
- 86 Breakout sessions

Following this year's successful event the upcoming 23rd RDA Plenary will take place in a hybrid format with the onsite event located in San José, Costa Rica between the 12-14 November, 2024.

RDA Group Acronyms

- Working Group - WG
- Interest Group - IG
- Birds of Feather - BoF
- Community of Practice - CoP

Summaries Section

Overview

This section contains shorter highlight recommendations and signposting. These are aimed at ELIXIR members to get info on key event sessions and other key links from the various RDA 22nd Plenary sessions of interest to members of the life sciences community, GDI project and ELIXIR RDM Community.

Highlight RDA sessions, progress & outputs for ELIXIR members

- **Updates and feedback on the FAIR4ML IG activities**
 - Session of key interest to the **ELIXIR Machine Learning (ML) Focus Group**.
 - Session details advances on metadata markup standards for ML models ([FAIR4ML schema](#)) and ML ready data sets ([croissant standard](#)).
 - [Session notes doc link](#) & [slides link](#)
 - [Notes link](#), page 11
- **Exploring the FAIR requirements for federated infrastructures in the life sciences and beyond**
 - **Gen3**: stood out as a key item of relevance for ELIXIR to look into. Useful for creating commons like structures. Great great **Galaxy** talk, FAIR data management aspects of support - <https://gen3.org/> (Australia cohort study usage) & Africa undertaking a pilot implementation.
 - [Session notes doc link](#)
 - [Notes link](#), page 20
- **Harmonising the Future of Multi-Omics Data Standards Integration**
 - Group is looking at multi-omics and standards in this space, of relevance to **ELIXIR Communities**. Do the ELIXIR Omics Communities - formal response/engagement plan? This group is global, important to keep ELIXIR involved and contributing.
 - Of relevance to **ELIXIR Data Platform WP2** on data brokering such as the work on the [MARS: Multi-omics Adapter for Repository Submissions](#).
 - Of relevance to database standards work in ELIXIR such as that from [FAIRsharing](#).
 - Action: monitor and retain contact with the group and leads, where opportunity for **ELIXIR Communities** in ELIXIR to contribute arise, communication to be maintained.
 - [Session notes doc link](#)
 - [Notes link](#), page 11
- **Criteria and Certification for trustworthy Technical Repository Service Providers**
 - [Case statement doc](#) - outlines the groups focus to tackle the landscape of trustworthy database repositories & potentially accreditation in this space.
 - Of relevance to:
 - **EOSC EDEN & EOSC FIDELIS** projects
 - **ELIXIR CDR & Data Platform** / ELIXIR database maintainers
 - CoreTrustSeal accreditation - of relevance to this group.
 - [Session notes doc](#)
 - [Notes link](#), page 15
- **Cross-community efforts in building services and professions for Data Stewards**

- ELIXIR **RDM Community** showcase by Mijke Jetten (ELIXIR-NL).
- [TeSS](#) interest for dissemination of training materials. Of note to **ELIXIR Training Platform**
- [Certification of RDM by Uni Vienna](#) - accreditation of certification for courses on RDM.
- Finland stakeholders - same type of workshop also will run soon, **ELIXIR-FI** folk involved.
- [Session notes doc](#)
- [Notes link](#), page 12

- **Policies in Research Organisations for Research Software (PRO₄RS) Working Group**
 - Software policy focused session and list of known policies to date collected by the WG: <https://www.researchsoft.org/software-policies/>
 - Of relevance for **ReSA**, **ELIXIR Tools Platform** and **EOSC EVERSE** stakeholders.
 - [Session web page](#)
 - [Notes link](#), page 14

- **RDA Ambassadors and Champions: Building an IG with lessons learned**
 - Focus on how useful such a group could be for leveraging outputs such as bringing external networks and infrastructure more firmly within RDA.
 - [Session notes doc](#)
 - [Notes link](#), page 16

Highlight RDA sessions of note to the **Genomic Data Infrastructure (GDI) project**

- **Exploring the FAIR requirements for federated infrastructures in the life sciences and beyond**
 - [Notes link](#), page 19

- **Harmonising the Future of Multi-Omics Data Standards Integration**
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Highlight RDA sessions of note to **ELIXIR RDM Community**

- **Active Data Management Plans: are we there yet?**
 - [Notes link](#), page 18

- **Navigating the Landscape Together: A Research Data Management Café**
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Notes section

Overview

This section contains more detailed notes by ELIXIR members at the event who reported back key info.

Note: not all sessions of the event had ELIXIR reporter coverage given the volume of sessions.

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Co-located Events / Sessions

[\[C002\] Advancing Genomic Data Governance: An Indian Perspective](#)

Session Reporting

- Overview with calendar links: [+ RDA-P22-Programme](#)
- All times are in UTC timezone.
- See [Example](#) to see how a session report could look like.

Plenary Sessions

[P001] Plenary Session: Opening RDA 22nd Plenary Meeting. 'Why establish national and regional RDA nodes in Europe? The communities perspective'

 When: 2024-05-14 09:30-11:00

 Reported by: Marek Suchánek

[Collaborative notes](#) (for more information)

[Hilary's introduction](#)

Alexandra Delipalta (RDA Europe Director of Operations, [see slides](#)) introduces the journey of RDA Europe so far (EC funding, RDA Europe 4.0 programme, EOSC Future RDA Open Calls, WorldFAIR, and other key milestones in recent years). Then, Alex presented mission, vision and priorities based on the RDA Association Strategic Priorities for 2023-2025 ([link](#)) where is mainly support and help to the European data community and advocacy on the global level. RDA Tiger/Tigrues services have been presented as essential for supporting WG activities.

European Partner and Committed countries - representative presentations

- France (Francoise Genova, [slides](#))
 - Highlights the importance of RDA having a voice nationally, and France having a strong voice within the formal RDA structure.
- The Netherlands (Margriet Miedema, [slides](#))
 - 25% of the RDA membership comes from the Netherlands, which makes them feel a kind of obligation / moral responsibility to support the RDA community
 - Supported by NWO funder
- UK via UKRI (Rachel Bruce, [slides](#))
 - Have established in the UK, an Int'l Research Data Initiatives Forum to develop a regional engagement liaison capability, and are currently identifying priority areas for focus, e.g. PIDs, data commons, repository standards/certification, research software, DAS; all things that ELIXIR regularly is engaged in. contact for further info: openresearch@ukri.org

There were general comments about how there could be increased communication among RDA country/regional nodes incl. Ireland and Portugal. One key point from the discussion was the need for national support or related funded projects. It was concluded that it is for the best if the activities are related to jobs of people involved (either as part of projects or non-project job).

[P005] Collaborating Internationally for Regional Benefit

 When: 2024-05-21 04:30-06:00

 Reported by: Marek Suchánek

There were two main aims of this session, to look at open-science platforms and to get perspective on CARE principles. Thus, the first presentation **CARE for Indigenous Data** by dr. Riley Taitingfond (University of Arizona) briefly explained what are indigenous data is and their sovereignty including different data principles related to such data. CARE Principles for Indigenous Data Governance were introduced while pointing the audience to <https://www.gida-global.org/care> website.

First national approach to open science was presented by Jung-Ho Um (Korea, KISTI). Korea has its research data platform **DataON** since 2021 for submitting, gathering, searching and analysing research data. It aggregates research data from various sources and then provides search & retrieval (powered by Elasticsearch and Kibana) as well as data analytics service using JupyterLab and Visual workflow. In terms of CARE principles, the platform is aligned (e.g. allows categorising data, providing authority to control, or detecting sensitive data by patterns).

Next, the Japanese approach to open science and CARE principles was presented by Mikiko Tanifuji (NII). [NII Research Data Cloud](#) (RDC) covers the entire data lifecycle by combining three platforms for data discovery ([CiNii Research](#)), data management ([GakuNinRDM](#)), and data publication ([JAIR Cloud](#) run by JPCOAR). It was explained that CARE principles can be taken into considerations while working on DMP and developing data governance for a project.

The final presentation on [Malaysia Open Science Platform](#) (MOSP) by Noorsaadah Abd. Rahman outlined the Malaysian journey since 2015 consisting of formation of Open Science initiatives and training data stewards. [Malaysia Open Science Alliance](#) (MOSA) consists of 14 institutions that are committed to OS practices. They have a training program on data stewardship, social media, open science guidelines and also an integrated database from 8 repositories. Currently running a pilot project developing the MOSP architecture. CARE principles are related to their national guidelines for open science including the research domain on indigenous knowledge.

[Poog] Closing 22nd Plenary Meeting

 When: 2024-05-23 16:30-18:00

 Reported by: Marek Suchánek

The session is dedicated to Latin America and the Caribbean to highlight Open Science, Research Data Management activities and stakeholders in the region. However, first Hilary Hanahoe gave an overview of RDA 22nd Plenary as this was the last session of the event (86 breakout sessions, 6 regional plenaries, 511 participants from 47 countries).

The following presentations were in Spanish:

- Lautaro Matas, Secretario Ejecutivo y Técnico - LA Referencia ([slides](#))
- Juan Maldini, ANII ([slides](#))
- Patricia Munoz Palma ([slides](#))

[LA Referencia](#) is Latin American Network for Open Science gives visibility to the scientific production of higher education and research institutions in Latin America, promotes open and free access to the full text, with special emphasis on publicly financed results. They collaborate with OpenAIRE and UNESCO but also various initiatives incl. European countries such as Portugal (PTCRIS) or Spain (FECYT/Recolecta). Currently, only 20% of repository contents in LA have DOIs; they have plans with decentralised ARK PIDs and will conduct pilots with different repositories. They are having different CRIS systems developed such as BrCRIS or PerúCRIS.

Breakout Sessions

[Soo2] Navigating the Landscape Together: A Research Data Management Café

 Group(s): IG Engaging Researchers with Data

 When: 2024-05-14 07:00-08:30

 Reported by: Marek Suchánek

The session was chaired by James Savage (IG chair); James introduced the session and the IG which is about implementing good RDM practice across all communities and institutions (sharing tools, best practices, resources to help organisations, etc.). There was a previous output, *Engaging Researchers with Data Management: The Cookbook* (<https://www.openbookpublishers.com/books/10.11647/obp.0185>), that consists of 24 case studies. They collect such case studies as effective and proven practices; not the other hand they don't want to build generic documentation nor bring together many details about large RDM support programmes; participants were motivated to contribute with their case studies.

Shannon Sheridan and Briana Ezray Wham shared their ideas and experience on using a podcast to engage with the data professional community. On podcasting platforms, they have *IDEA: Improving data Engagement and Advocacy* (e.g. on [Spotify](#)) where they interview professionals and review new relevant literature. Afterwards, there were two group discussions - one focusing on DMPs and other on data sharing, reuse, and preservation (details in [collaborative notes](#)).

[Soo3] Health Data Commons: GORC international model profiling towards FAIR convergence

 Group(s): BoF

 When: 2024-05-14 07:00-08:30 (repeat: 2024-05-21 07:00-08:30)

 Reported by: Wolmar Nyberg Åkerström

This [BoF session](#) proposed the formation of a new RDA group to create a health-data-focused profile for the outputs of the Global Open Research Commons (GORC) IG and GORC International Model WG ([see also notes from the session So16 below](#)). The session opened with an introduction to how this activity would contribute to connecting different health data commons—to each other and to data commons in other areas—and some of the related challenges—such as metadata, semantic and syntactic interoperability, and federated reuse of sensitive data. The major part of the session was focused on discussions to develop a [case statement \(vo.1\) for the proposed group](#). Proposed co-chairs included Lars Eklund from ELIXIR Sweden and Lauren Maxwell from University of Heidelberg.

The session's key points were summarised in the [collaborative notes](#) as follows:

There is interest and need in the health data and health digital research infrastructure environment to enable visibility and transparency in the choices made by these infrastructures on how they implement FAIR as well as their underlying structures. The GORC international model V1.0 is a reasonable starting point to create such a set of profiles of health data commons implementations and the proposed Health Data Commons GORC profile WG should move forward for TAB and community review. In addition to a close collaboration with the GORC IM WG, the proposed WG will need to maintain close collaboration with the Life Science Data Infrastructure IG in particular, as well as connection with several RDA and external groups working on complimentary projects.

Highlight from the case statement of the proposed group [Health Data Commons GORC Profile WG](#):

- Background: Health data commons have been or are being launched across a number of geographies. Advance FAIR convergence and interoperability for health data. Enabling country- and cross-country or global analyses of health data. Support sharing of implementation decisions made across different health data commons and contribute to identifying gaps in cross-commons interoperability.
- The group aims to: Adapt the GORC International Model to country-level or transnational health data commons with some focus on interoperability and sensitive data concerns. Use the model to describe and analyse how different health data commons are being implemented and derive some form of knowledge graph that maps to other types of commons.
- Proposed engagement with groups/initiatives includes RDA where ELIXIR is involved, EOSC Association Task Forces and other data communities such as CODATA, and a range of Health Data Infrastructures (including the Rare Disease platform from EJP-RD/ERDERA, EHDS, and ELIXIR).
- Deliverables: 1) Health Data Commons profile of the GORC model. 2) Network graph describing the actual or planned implementation of health data commons using the HDC GORC profile. 3) If within scope and time limits, consider how this feeds into FAIR assessment for health commons
- See current [draft case statement \(vo.2\)](#) and [case statement submitted for RDA group review](#).

Recordings:

- [BoF Health Data Commons GORC international model profiling towards FAIR convergence](#)
- [REPEAT BoF Health Data Commons GORC international model profiling towards FAIR convergence](#)

[Soo6] RDA in the Evaluation of Research Landscape

 Group(s): IG Evaluation of Research

 When: 2024-05-14 14:00-15:30 (repeat: 2024-05-21 22:30-00:00)

 Reported by: Marek Suchánek

Francoise Genova gave an introduction about the meeting agenda, interest group, its goals and timeline. This group has been active since Plenary 21 (new group) and since then there were several presentations in different venues. Then, Francoise continued with the presentation *RDA Role in the Evaluation of Research Landscape*. The first key activity is to contribute to a typology of concepts/activities related to EoR (possible metrics & criteria, stakeholder representation, research outputs & properties, disciplinary aspects). In this activity, they collaborate with Data Usage Metrics WG and Sharing Rewards and Credit (SHARC) IG; for representing stakeholders, Early Career and Engagement IG and Data Policy Standardisation and Implementation IG are involved. Finally, for research outputs, they are working with Software Source Code IG and Physical Samples and Collections IG. Their [output is in draft mode](#) and they welcome any feedback or other contributions (to be submitted on 11 June). Then also collaboration plans with the [CoARA Working Groups](#) has been introduced briefly.

[Soo8] Harmonising the Future of Multi-Omics Data Standards Integration

 Group(s): WG RDA-OfR Creating a Multi-omics Metadata Schema Standard Reporting Matrix

 When: 2024-05-14 14:00-15:30 (repeat: 2024-05-22 22:30-00:00)

 Reported by: Allyson Lister

Of particular interest for ELIXIR Communities for Metabolomics, Proteomics, Single-Cell Omics, and others.

They are looking for ELIXIR feedback around their [current landscape review](#) and upcoming FAIRsharing collection. ELIXIR members will be able to use these deliverables to assess, update, and/or refine current domain standards

recommendations that have a direct link to an affiliated ELIXIR resource. Current ELIXIR Omics standards can be evaluated to other global standards outside the ELIXIR node for developing new integrations with other complimentary record resources by browsing the collection once completed.

The upcoming FAIRsharing Multi-Omics collection will be a first of its kind in terms of global aggregation of standards across multiple initiatives, societies, and consortium efforts agnostic to subject matter topic areas. We also have incorporated the RDMkit lifecycle into our landscape review so members can selectively evaluate how these standards apply in relation to data management planning.

[Soog] Updates and feedback on the FAIR4ML IG activities

 Group(s): IG FAIR for Machine Learning (FAIR4ML)

 When: 2024-05-14 14:00-15:30 (*repeat*: 2024-05-21 22:30-00:00)

 Reported by: Gavin Farrell & Fotis Psomopoulos

- [Session notes doc link](#) & [slides link](#)
- Initial landscape mapping of stakeholders & projects of [interest](#).

- Task Force 1: how to apply FAIR principles to ML (Fotis Psomopoulos - ELIXIR-GR)
 - Diverse challenge - from software or workflows, etc - custom application guidelines needed
 - Defining an ML model is hard → data/software/parameters/mix?
 - Working on a [whitepaper](#) for this
 - At literature review stage → [Zotero groups](#)
 - ML - [Life cycle image](#)
 - FAIR - data/software/ML
 - Exercise in notes to identify FAIR considerations for these
 - Comment from attendee: <https://zenodo.org/records/10407265> - a paper describing the ML lifecycle

- Task Force 2: Metadata for ML models (Daniel Garijo Verdejo - UPM)
 - [Lit review](#) → Schema.org profile (search engine findability for ML)
 - [Crosswalk work](#) against current vocabularies & Huggingface model cards (these are Readme sections for your GitHub on ML model)
 - [First joint schema vocab release - vo.01](#): 'FAIR4ML schema'
 - To be consulted and worked on → via RDA site
 - JSON-LD schema format
 - Most terms borrowed from existing ones on schema.org
 - + from Codemeta vocab also - which is used for research software
 - ELSI aspects, cross links, +
 - Documentation page soon
 - Examples needed for feedback
 - HF model cards - YAML format
 - Goal → machine readable ML model metadata
 - Discussion
 - How to ensure cross-domain use vs Bio focused? → completely domain agnostic metadata, allows extendability
 - Huggingface does not have model versioning
 - ML model quantisation field - important metadata aspect for redeployment feasibility

- LLM page of interest from software heritage:
 - <https://www.softwareheritage.org/2023/10/19/swh-statement-on-llm-for-code/>
- Note:
 - [Croissant](#) for ML ready datasets metadata
 - [FAIR4ML schema](#) for ML model metadata
- Croissant - (Omar Benjelloun - Google)
 - [Google dataset search](#)
 - [ML Commons](#) & [Open ML](#)
 - Based on schema.org/dataset → extend with missing info
 - Characteristics of ML data that are unique
 - Croissant layers
 - Dataset level metadata
 - Resource description
 - Content structure
 - ML semantics
 - Benefits
 - Homogenous ML dataset corpus
 - Better search and discovery
 - Better tool interop to work on dataset repos in same way if all using croissant eg: load easy from Kaggle/HF/etc into pytorch/tensroflow/etc
 - ML users focus less on data related tasks but instead working on and evaluating models
 - Tools to create croissant dataset exist
 - Responsible AI (RAI) - attributes in croissant for finability
 - [Core RAI vocabulary](#) → data life cycle, labelling, compliance, + - use cases in mind
 - [Croissant editor](#) / [GitHub](#)
 - Status
 - 400k datasets in HF/Kaggle/OpenML
 - Google dataset can filter by croissant datasets
 - Arxiv paper on Croissant: <https://arxiv.org/pdf/2403.19546>
 - DCAT relations noted

[So10] Cross-community efforts in building services and professions for Data Stewards

 Group(s): IG Professionalising Data Stewardship

 When: 2024-05-14 14:00-15:30 (*repeat:* 2024-05-16 07:00-08:30)

 Reported by: Federico Bianchini (attended the *repeat* session)

Origin: lack of consensus on the role of a data steward, confusion about what DSs are meant to be doing. This hampers the realisation of the profession and the building up of capacity at organisational level.

Group started in 2019, 9 task groups with different focus. Starting from terminology and models, shift to career tracs and how to further develop. Data St. as a (i) service (advise/repo/training) and (ii) profession (manager/curator/scientist). [duality]

3 tasks presenting, models, careers, network

Task 1 models

Global survey over 200 responses regarding organisational models, available on Zenodo. Focus on database of use cases from different organisation at different stages of maturity. [we should check if ELIXIR is there and to what extent]. Welcoming new members. On June 6th there will be a call open to all.

Task2 Career

Completed a survey as well w connected report, also on Zenodo.

Lack of human capacity to go through the data. Dataset available on Zenodo for other people to work with it.

Questions on educational background of DSs, actual job titles, questions about future perspectives. Next steps: connect with similar initiatives (e.g. EOSC task force, skills4EOSC, + similar). Case statement for RDA WG in prep. On developing DS persona

Task3: Network

Place to connect and get info on training. Encourage the creation oif new globval networks.

New members required. Skills4EOSC project well represented.

Cross-community efforts: IG data policy standardisation

- Increase FAIRness of policies. Focus on funders and publishers. DS are key stakeholders in this context.
- Libraries for Research data: Aggregates various areas of interest. Finland received funding for piloting training for DS. Self thought specialist to transition to something better. DS not visible in career path. In 2021 a group was put together, report on Zenodo. Plan to get a curriculum to data stewards.

. Extensive cooperation required, Finland will collaborate with Austria. Starting next year in March.

From the chat: [me]

I can probably share that we are attempting something similar in Norway, although with more of a Life Science focus:

<https://zenodo.org/records/7689715>

[got lost in the chat, missed some contributions, but quite some focus on training which is relevant to us]

Carpentry model ofr training mentioned.

DS as glue in organisations. There are, however, several types of DS.

Discussion: 3 questions in the chat.

Discussion on handbook for DS from ELIXIR RDM community.

Focus on people DS. Exemple from NL. Many people will join a contentanthon this month [I will]

[I did get to describe TeSS to the group, hopefully I did a decent job]

Mijke described this: <https://elixir-europe-training.github.io/ELIXIR-TrP-FAIR-Converge/>

DS new in South Africa. There was a recent focus starting from EOSC. The community is unaware of this new role.

CODATA summer schools (online) is accessible (low fee as well). Cost and access is typically a challenge. ELIXIR is helping with this. RDA is crucial to bring people to the topic.

There is a lot of interest in training, but there should be more control. Accessibility is crucial, thinking also about size of organisations and projects.

[So12] Data Management Challenges and Solutions for Research Institutions in Africa and Latin America

 Group(s): IG Research Data Architectures in Research Institutions

 When: 2024-05-14 14:00-15:30

 Reported by: Marek Suchánek

James Wilson (UCL) chaired the session and explained the agenda of the meeting as well as gave introduction to RDARI (Research Data Architectures for Research Institutions) IG. Today's topics are challenges in Africa and South America and how to overcome them, emerging innovations, architectures for interoperability and exchange, examples of local projects.

Then, a series of short talks followed:

- Muliaro Wafula (African Open Science Platform) briefly introduced the [GOSCloud](#); they have federated websites and are building a trusted research environment with federated access.
- Mattia Vaccari (UCT) presented the IDIA Science Gateway, mainly its supercomputing centre and its usage (almost 500 users, 80% utilisation); towards Science Gateways, fully searchable index and **SA Open Science Cloud (learning from EOSC)**.
- Lautaro Mata (LA Referencia) talked about the activities in Open Science within Latin America: PIDs coverage (**dARK = decentralised, blockchain-based ARK PIDs**) and the roadmap for 2024.

Brief discussions and wrap up followed (more details in the [collaborative notes](#)).

[So14] FAIRification of Genomic Annotations – metadata harmonisation at scale

 Group(s): WG FAIRification of Genomic Annotations

 When: 2024-05-14 22:30-00:00 (*repeat:* 2024-05-23 14:00-15:30)

 Reported by: Gavin Farrell (Hub)

- [Notes doc](#)
- [Group charter](#)
- Sveinung Gundersen (ELIXIR-NO), key contact point for this group's efforts.

[So15] Policies in Research Organisations for Research Software (PRO₄RS) Working Group

 Group(s): WG RDA & ReSA: Policies in Research Organisations for Research Software (PRO₄RS)

 When: 2024-05-14 22:30-00:00 (*repeat:* 2024-05-23 07:00-08:30)

 Reported by: Allyson Lister

[Notes](#)

- This session was focused around policies that include software (possibly as well as other digital objects such as data).
- The policy list so is at far <https://www.researchsoft.org/software-policies/>, with <https://forms.gle/wavjA26qmXPP3Je78> being the form for adding research software policies to database
- ELIXIR may well wish to participate with regards to research software policies? They mainly focus on institutions, but there are also regional policies - does ELIXIR/EOSC have an infrastructure policy around software?

[So16] Global open research commons: model adoption and next steps

 Group(s): WG GORC International Model, IG Global Open Research Commons

 When: 2024-05-14 22:30-00:00 (*repeat:* 2024-05-22 14:00-15:30)

 Reported by: Wolmar Nyberg Åkerström

This joint group session ([agenda](#)) focused on presenting the taxonomy of elements, International Model (GORC IM) and the other supporting outputs related to the Global Open Research Commons (GORC) related RDA activities and to pave the way for submitting the GORC IM for RDA recommendation. The session highlighted and discussed applications and potential adoption cases from a Norwegian RI related funding proposal ([REASON - ResEARch CommonSfOr Norway](#)), examples from SURF (NL) and their National Program Open Science (NPOS), potential uses in ELIXIR / Science for Life Laboratory (SciLifeLab) Sweden.

The session's key points were summarised in the [collaborative notes](#) as follows:

The GORC IG Typology of Essential Elements is very useful as a discussion starter and prompt for commons stakeholders. The model is useful as is, but would benefit from some revisions, evidence of relevance through framework mapping, implementation profiles, and a more interactive, friendly container. Support for adopters is an ongoing need, as well as showcasing the value and impact of using the model for various stakeholder groups.

Supporting outputs from the GORC related RDA activities:

- [GORC IG: Typology and Definitions](#) – describes a typology of 9 essential elements in a Commons based on careful discussions within the group and a process of consultation and refinement over 4 years. Named contributors include people affiliated with EOSC Association & EC. See also the [GORC IG: Typology and Definitions Diagram](#) for a high-resolution version of the image used to present the typology.
- [The Global Open Research Commons International Model](#) (GORC IM) – expands on each element with a structured set of attributes and descriptions sourced from a wide range of resources and extensive input from the global community. Named contributors include people affiliated with ELIXIR, EOSC Association & EC. See also the [GORC IM Report](#) that expands on the intent of the model and how the attributes were identified and structured.

The session concludes with an open discussion on how to structure future work on GORC related activities and what to focus on, such as: supporting adoption and capturing related feedback; mappings or alignment with other well-established models/frameworks; expanding on the model with guidance on potential solutions for the considerations linked to each attribute in the current version of the GORC IM; or proposing some sort of maturity assessment model.

GORC related activities will continue to be discussed in the GORC IG. A new WG (GORC II WG?) is proposed to continue the work on the model by developing a starter kit to support for new adopters as well as to develop profiles of the model that are more closely mapped to specific types of commons / RIs and keeping a registry of these. The groups also discussed how to explore synergies/collaborations with the RDA National Data Services IG and the Mapping the landscape of digital research tools WG.

Recordings:

- [Global open research commons model adoption and next steps RDA VP22 BO3](#)
- [REPEAT: Global open research commons: model adoption and next steps](#)

[So19] Criteria and Certification for trustworthy Technical Repository Service Providers

 Group(s): WG Community-based catalogue of requirements for trustworthy Technical Repository Service Providers Working Group (TRSPs WG)

 When: 2024-05-15 07:00-08:30 (repeat: 2024-05-22 07:00-08:30)

 Reported by: Gavin, Allyson (Allyson was at the repeat session)

- [Notes links](#)
- [Miro activity](#)
- Of primary interest for ELIXIR is that this WG would like to reach out to us to learn about ELIXIR procedures around CDRs and RIRs, as well as a number of other infrastructures/communities such as RDA France, RDA Publisher IG, ARDC
- Demand and Supply = there are many datasets that are being created, but only a few certified repositories via CoreTrustSeal for example. This group is focusing on rate of certification (cost/complexity, bar too high, too costly and complex), scope of certification, and inclusion of service providers.
- Having a method by which other repositories may show their credentials in an lightweight way would perhaps solve many of the issues with certification coverage, inclusion, cost and complexity that currently exist.
- This means that there is a tie-in here to, for example, the RDA DRA WG outputs, which is also relevant for ELIXIR as relates to Allyson (ELIXIR-UK and co-chair of DRA WG) and the data repository attributes that should be exposed if following the final outputs (<https://doi.org/10.15497/RDA00103>) of this group.

[So20] Translating the Data Versioning Principles into Machine Actionable Recommendations

 Group(s): IG Data Versioning

 When: 2024-05-15 07:00-08:30

 Reported by: Marek Suchánek

Mingfanf Wu (ARDC) introduced the session and also provided an overview of the IG including its history since RDA P8 (2016). Jens Klump gave a brief refresher on the data versioning principles and why it is needed in machine actionable form. They collected 39 use cases and published a paper in Data Science Journal (in 2021, [10.5334/dsj-2021-012](https://doi.org/10.5334/dsj-2021-012)). They reuse [FRBR](#); [BIBFRAME](#) has been discussed but will not be adopted but they get inspiration/**align with software versioning**.

Afterwards, there were six questions/topics for discussion and online contributions in the [shared meeting document](#). Also discussions followed up with identifying other related IGs/WGs. Finally, there was also a call for a **new co-chair of the IG** as Kirsten Elger is stepping down.

From the questions, there are certain points that participants agreed on (and which may be reflected in the future work of this IG):

- **Fixing of errors** that have been reported by users of the data as well as **data cleaning** should result in a new release/version.
- Metadata can change without changing the data. **Metadata should be versioned**. Corrections to metadata should be versioned to provide provenance.
- Person(s) responsible for the change/new version should be captured (provenance)
- Rather than numbering or naming, **versions need to have a (persistent) identifier**. And it should be clearly stated how versioning works in a repository.
- A **data citation should contain the full identifier**, always including the version identifier (for reproducibility and many other reasons).

[So21] RDA Ambassadors and Champions: Building an IG with lessons learned

 Group(s): RDA in Ireland, WG FAIRsharing Registry: Connecting data policies, standards and databases RDA

 When: 2024-05-15 07:00-08:30 (repeat: 2024-05-16 22:30-00:00)

 Reported by: Allyson Lister

[notes](#)

This session was very well attended, and was an interactive discussion on how a possible IG would look that is primarily focused around engagement and outreach in a cross-disciplinary and inter-regional manner, leveraging the existing knowledge of alumni ambassadors from past EOSC-funded awards.

There was a lot of support for such an IG, and awareness that it could work well with the Early Career Researchers and Engagement IG.

Primary focus was on how useful such a group could be for leveraging of outputs; bringing external networks and infrastructure more firmly within RDA; and the ability to facilitate cross-WG and cross-network collaboration opportunities. There was also talk of particular RDA volunteer roles to be linked to this; e.g. if a project such as ELIXIR wanted to engage more closely with RDA e.g. via a webinars or training material or factsheets, the ELIXIR rep could gain one of these roles for a year, and consequently gain the 'official backing' of the RDA. This may well be useful at different times and for different projects within the RDA.

[So23] Infrastructures for Research Software: Moving toward adoption

 Group(s): IG Software Source Code

 When: 2024-05-15 14:00-15:30 (repeat: 2024-05-22 22:30-00:00)

 Reported by: Marek Suchánek

The session was chaired traditionally by Morane Gruenpeter ([Software Heritage](#)). Morane introduced the Software Source Code IG as well as its past and current activities. Software is a pillar of Open Science in their view and they want to **make software a first class output**. [Research software lifecycle](#) and **Scholarly Infrastructures for Research Software** (SIRS, and related [Gap Analysis](#)) were briefly presented. Then, Morane gave a short demo of Software Heritage on how source code can be archived there and Lars Holm Nielsen continued with an example on Zenodo. Maud Medves presented **HAL** ([hal.science](#), multidisciplinary open archive for sharing research outputs) and its integration with Software Heritage.

After the presentations and demonstrations, an interactive part with a prepared set of questions followed. Participants filled in the document with their experience e.g. what is the current status around research software within an institution, research software FAIRness, or how they encourage researchers to follow guidelines (more information and answers can be found in the [meeting document](#)).

[S[So26] NTRO Gaggles – Boosting non text support through experiential and collaborative effort

 Group(s): BoF

 When: 2024-05-15 14:00-15:30 (repeat: 2024-05-16 22:30-00:00)

 Reported by: Allyson Lister

[Notes](#)

I joined this as I was curious about what NTROs are (non-text or non-traditional research outputs), where these outputs can be processes or products as well as more traditional outputs. While primarily in the Social Sciences / Humanities domain, we may find this of increasing relevance in the future with ELIXIR.

Broadly it was a session about furthering standardisation and FAIRness of such non-traditional products (how do you make a video of a dance FAIR? What about participatory science?), with discussions including how to enable inclusivity within RDM of these NTROs by recognition of NTROs and practice research generally in the context of FAIR Research.

However, there are places where this work will likely intersect with what ELIXIR members do. One example is citizen science. Citizen science is a type of participatory science and as such falls within the NTRO category. For most participatory action and citizen science research the topic of FAIR and CARE, and in particular identification and attribution of those citizens who should be credited, is a hurdle because disclosing the identity of participants is difficult. Further issues around what - out of a whole plethora of digital objects associated with participatory science - can and should be usefully shared and made FAIR - is a tricky subject.

[So28] Active Data Management Plans: are we there yet?

 Group(s): IG Active Data Management Plans, WG DMP Common Standards

 When: 2024-05-15 14:00-15:30

 Reported by: Bianchini, Marek Suchánek

Elli Papadopoulou (ARC, chair of the IG) gave an introduction to the session. It started with Menti polls to find out more about the audience (mainly European-based, different domains, focused on DMPs). A series of short talks followed:

- Kevin Ashley (DCC) provided an overview and history of the IG and WG as well as insights for possible future work.
- Marek Suchánek (CTU/DSW) presented that the **WG is in maintenance mode but there are big changes needed** (e.g. more machine-actionable specification, RDF representation, enabling extensions, cleanup, and APIs that specify the “**actions**” for machine-**actionable** DMPS). It leads potentially to creating a new WG(s) to drive the work on these tasks.
- Tomasz Miksa presented the **Salzburg manifesto on maDMPs** (from the previous plenary) which resides at <https://activedmps.org/> and he invited others to support the manifesto.
- Elli presented the new Horizon Europe project OSTrails (ostrails.eu) that connects DMPs, SKGs, FAIR assessment, and other supporting RDM services. For the DMP part, maDMPs are the essential core for all the work and interoperability & solving related issues (better exchange of information, DMPs might not be deposited or published, FAIR assessment is equally not available, the dataset is not connected to potentially FAIRifying resources such as DMP. In the project, the main DMP platforms are represented (Argos, DSW, DAMAP) and will build common API and evaluation services for DMPs.

Discussion followed tackling the following topics:

- DMPID linked to ORCID
- Link to RE3DATA?
 - Moving information around is crucial, not focussing on specific cases.
 - There are a number of groups aiming at this.
- Test cases? Establish processes for compliant objects? But what is the time-frame, who would do it?
- Ontologies? How do we want to define a standard?
 - Standard is both describing the elements and their expression/representation
 - F AIRsharing mentioned for NIH-related DMP as source of PIDs
- Looking for license information? Are we using it?
- A DMP must have an identifier (not necessarily a DOI)
- This might cause inconsistency in the interoperability,
- A balance need to be achieved between what we require and what would work for different groups.

- CrossReef's Funding Registry is sunseting in favor of ROR: <https://ror.readme.io/docs/funder-registry>
[Exemplary spreadsheet](#)
- We need to define actions that we want from a maDMP
 - What information to parse? Do we have what we need?
 - And FAIR assessment around this is crucial
- Changing a funder's mind is a slow process.
- Evaluation is a very important topic, especially how to automatise it for funders.
 - A score is desired, also to avoid hiring DMP reviewers.

Key notes from the meeting chat:

- Regarding DMP tools, templates and the maDMP common standard: I am currently involved in a project on aligning DMP guidance (including adapting a template) as well as another project on evaluating DMP tools. Something that we figured out in this work is that, although this is not evident for users, it is important to separate/communicate clearly what is functionalities of a tool (which enable compliance with the standard) and DMP templates (which may or may not require certain values). Another take away from the work is that there is many stakeholders with diverging expectations towards DMPs - an institution that wants to raise awareness for storage guidelines has not the same interest as a funder that likes to track project outputs (feedback appreciated: <https://zenodo.org/records/10836868>).
- Diverging stakeholder expectations
- We did some very basic landscaping activity on what could be automated, but we definitely need more discussion and viewpoints: <https://datascience.codata.org/articles/10.5334/dsj-2023-028>

[So30] Exploring the FAIR requirements for federated infrastructures in the life sciences and beyond

 Group(s): IG Life Science Data Infrastructures

 When: 2024-05-15 22:30-00:00 (repeat: 2024-05-22 07:00-08:30)

 Reported by: Rob Hooft, Wolmar Nyberg Åkerström

This IG session aimed to showcase successful and promising approaches for federating infrastructures in the biomolecular life sciences to inform a discussion with the wider RDA community on opportunities for future work and collaborations. The sessions opened with presentations on two topics that served as examples of state of the art in the life sciences followed by flash talks on complementary/other promising approaches for connecting FAIR data resources and services. The topics focused examples from the Global Alliance for Genomics and Health (GA4GH) and Galaxy communities with presenters on human genomic data from Australian BioCommons, African H3ABioNet & the European 1+Million Genomes Initiative/GDI and FAIR data analysis from Galaxy Australia and Galaxy Europe.

Detailed notes and report by Wolmar can be found in the [collaborative notes document](#) where the sessions discussions were summarised as follows:

The session highlighted various approaches to enable seamless data discovery and analysis across regionally dispersed and heterogeneous resources. Presenters shared insights from building on technical standards such as those developed by GA4GH, broadly used platforms such as Galaxy and frameworks such as 1+MG Framework to enable FAIR and secure data management in compute intensive domains, such as genomics. Discussions emphasised future opportunities to involve a wider range of infrastructures and efforts to align general and discipline specific infrastructure solutions.

Recordings:

- [15th May Exploring the FAIR requirements for federated infrastructures in the life sciences and beyond](#)
- [22nd May Exploring the FAIR requirements for federated infrastructures in the life sciences and beyond](#)

Summary notes from presentations on 15th May (Wolmar):

Talk by Bernie Pope & Oliver Hofmann – Exemplar projects that are using existing and upcoming GA4GH standards in the data infrastructure world - globally and in Australia

Part 1 by Bernie [[recording 18:51](#)]: Covered examples from genomic cohort data sharing and more specifically the activities linked to the Australian Cardiovascular Disease Data Commons (ACDC). Bernie provided an overview of motivations, goals and activities including processes and the technical platform inspired by NHLBI's BioData Catalyst based on Gen3.

Part 2 by Oliver [[recording 35:51](#)]: Covered Australian Genomics and how it supports clinical flagship projects and making data available for future research. Oliver presented components and features of a system to capture and make data accessible including links to GA4GH and other standards to support discovery, access and workflow execution. Work towards agreement on what a research environment looks like for different use cases and to be able to move data on demand and a national genomics infrastructure aligned with international initiatives.

Talk by Gareth Price – Towards a global harmonised biodata analysis infrastructure - the [use galaxy effort](#)

[[recording 50:31](#)] Covered Galaxy's user facing features such as uploading/accessing data, launching tools, and workflow creation and sharing as well as the useGalaxy servers, the Galaxy ToolShed (~10,000 tools), job distribution using Pulsar and metrics using the Total Perspective Vortex (TPV) abstraction layer. Gareth also talked about the role of groups, such as the Intergalactic Utilities Commission (IUC) and Intergalactic Workflow Commission (IWC), in managing common resources such as tools, containers, and workflows, including links to Dockstore and WorkflowHub.

Flashtalk by Wolmar Nyberg Åkerström (on behalf of Melissa Konopko) – [European '1+ Million Genomes' Initiative](#) and [European Genomic Data Infrastructure \(GDI\)](#)

[[recording 1:17:29](#)] Covered the 1+ Million Genomes initiative focusing a pitch for the [1+MG Framework](#) as a global reference point to connect to the European Genomic Data Infrastructure (GDI). Wolmar shared key messages and links in the chat to encourage the global community to [use the framework](#) and to [contribute to it](#) while highlighting GDI milestones, such as [GDI 18 months milestone](#) and [GDI Starter Kit milestone](#). Commenters highlighted that the framework has already been incredibly helpful to other efforts (e.g. Australia) and how the distinction between required/recommended/informational labels would be helpful to support applications across actors at different levels of resourcing/maturity.

Notes from presentations on 22nd May (Rob):

Talk by Takudzwa Nyasha Musarurwa - Implementing [GA4GH](#) standards for federated data analysis in Africa

Description of extensive and already operating infrastructure for analysis of genomic data in Africa. Federated infrastructure based. Use case on infectious disease.

Talk by Bjoern Gruening – FAIR data analysis on Galaxy

Galaxy supports many of the ELIXIR communities, with tools for researchers but also as a training infrastructure. Focus of the talk on distributed and federated storage. Metadata annotation: Schema.org

Collaboration with GH4GH:

Beacon, TRS, DRS, TES

Galaxy is about abstraction layers

Galaxy is community agnostic:

Community sharing a framework

DL cycle figure from RDMkit shown without linking the source!

Export analysis to various platforms (GDrive, AWS)

Support for RO-CRATE.

Sharing is fundamental. You can also get public link.

This is true for data, visualisation, workflows and everything else

Wizard for best practices on workflows (e.g. "please add a licence")

Integration with WorkflowHub registry

Integration with Rstudio and Jupyter notebook as standard tools

You can mix HPC work in this interactive framework

Standard quota on the European server are 250 GB per user. Users are forced this way to clean up when they want to do new analyses.

In total, the server now has 3PB of data currently in use – scalability issue > federated solutions > 7 national instances in Europe

Both storage and compute infrastructure for the GALAXY service are federated over Europe by the server. Jobs can be routed to be executed close to where the data is stored.

Options explored to save on storage for the server and still increase functionality for the users:

- Not importing RAW data (use links instead), only results
- Let users use additional scratch space, which is cleaned up automatically.
- Bring your own storage
 - A user can choose their own object store where information is stored.

RO-crate strongly endorsed

Export to permanent archives such as Zenodo, identifier goes back to galaxy

You can reimport things from Zenodo

Optimise job scheduling via federated solution (pick the comp. Resource closer to me)

Flash talk by Rob Hooft: 1+MG framework

27 countries in Europe, sitting together to realise their desire to share human genomic data for research and other use. They have written up many of their decisions in the 1+MG framework. Several projects have been working on the infrastructure, writing up good practices and decisions in the framework. Current project is GDI, which is developing the technical infrastructure. Other project, Genome of Europe, will be working on a "representation" of the European population in the infrastructure.

Important goal: Remove the borders for data (EU law!). GDPR and all its special conditions for the highly sensitive data to be taken into account.

Appointments made are about the interfaces between the countries: every country needs to support the same functionality, but every country can use different tools for offering these based on availability, and based on how they fit into the national infrastructures (which can be wildly different between countries).

Interoperability between the implementations has to happen.

Requirements for security need to be in place, countries will need to share information on possible weaknesses in components.

All data is organised as datasets, DCAT ontology to describe the data and locate them + central resource to locate the data; this makes the resource compatible with EU standards for data exchange.

GH4GH standards are playing a major role.

Flash talk by Sveinung Gundersen: sensitive data in virtual RE

This talk explains how “crypt4GH” can play a role in many phases of genomic data infrastructure.

“A tourist's guide”

1. Trust the Chain of Trust – who watches the watchmen
2. Delegate Access to data
3. Enable geo-location of data
4. Secure data at all stages
5. Orchestrate federate data
6. Provide a user controlled solution
 - a. GH4GH standards for everything
 - b. Crypt4ghc relevant to everything but policies

Crypt4gh: under-appreciated part of the standard is header re-encryption: if user provides a key-pair you can re-encrypt without touching the datasets

Trusted exchange of public keys required

End-to-end implementation in Galaxy

Deferred dataset to decouple data (no central storage, data stays in TRE)

Flash talk by Rory McNeil: Tool interoperability in research clouds

Implementation of the GORC model

Storage layer is core, using DataCite DOIs and iRODS implementation.

[So36] Bridging the gaps between policy, coalface and data science in crisis situations

 Group(s): WG RDA / CODATA Data Systems, Tools, and Services for Crisis Situations

 When: 2024-05-16 07:00-08:30

 Reported by: Allyson Lister

[Notes](#)

I am a member of the UNESCO / CODATA working group on the creation of a toolkit for data policy in times of crisis (UNESCO DPTC Toolkit), and as such I attended this session as this WG is where the UNESCO WG intersects with the RDA. There is a high relevance to ELIXIR, as many times of crisis involve life science data (the pandemic being the obvious example).

The majority of this session revolved around the role of a data scientist, as data is needed before, during and after events, and data scientists (and their institutions and infrastructure) need to plan ahead so that ad hoc decisions about storage, manipulation, formatting analysis of data during an emergency is minimal. During crises, data scientists need access to real time, accurate, trustable data. Much of the heavy lifting can be done if data scientists are part of a network, and such a network (e.g. ELIXIR, EOSC) could implement particular crisis policies based on the emerging work by the UNESCO DPTC.

[So40] Revitalising data policy impact and alignment

 Group(s): IG Data policy standardisation and implementation

 When: 2024-05-16 14:00-15:30

 Reported by: Allyson Lister

[Notes](#)

The [revised charter](#) received positive feedback from the session participants, and will be circulated for one final round of feedback via the IG's email list. ELIXIR members may wish to utilise this IG as a connectivity, engagement and advocacy resource when looking to create policies, or perform comparisons of the policy landscape. FAIRsharing, an ELIXIR RIR, was described in the context of this IG as a source of policy metadata and as a place for such landscape analyses to be performed.

[So47] Research Tool Usage in Data Curation Workflows: Responsibilities & Collaboration

 Group(s): BoF

 When: 2024-05-21 07:00-08:30 (repeat: 2024-05-22 14:00-15:30)

 Reported by: Allyson Lister

[notes](#)

This BoF session focuses on exploring practical challenges of adopting and maintaining a healthy institutional RDM practice that relies on utilizing Research Tools to support data curation workflows.

Marek S from DSW was one of the presenters.

- Much of Data curation is still manual or semi-automated.
- Could be relevant to ELIXIR in the context of getting researchers to use (in an integrated, sensible way) the various tools developed by our members.
- Perspective from NH: While researchers are pretty good at using a single tool, there is often not the integration within their workflows that has them using a series of tools.
- MS: discuss integration possibilities with RSpace (update DMPs directly from ELN, link to a living / dynamic DMP from Rspace, exchange PIDs, Store documents generated by DSW within RSpace, create directory structure and files in rspace based on DMP)

Co-located Events / Sessions

[Coo2] Advancing Genomic Data Governance: An Indian Perspective

When: 2024-05-20 10:30-12:30

Reported by: Gavin Farrell (Hub)

- [Youtube of the session](#)